

THE EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILL TO INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Tursunboeva Mavjudakhon Shukurillo kizi,
Independent researcher
Pedagogical institute by Andijan State University

Abstract: *This article discover the teacher's tactics in teaching speaking and students' understanding of and attitudes toward teaching approaches for the speaking skill. This paper reveals a reasonable amount of acceptance of teaching methods for the speaking skill, but a widespread lack of understanding of such requirements. As a result of gender, educational qualifications, and years of experience, attitudes improved, but awareness and concepts were not verified.*

Key words: *effective strategy, teaching process, speaking skill, successful learning strategy, activity, students, classroom, methods*

Teaching is the process of passing on information to students about a topic. The goal of the learning process is for pupils to acquire knowledge and be able to comprehend it. To attain the goal of teaching, the instructor must be innovative in selecting resources and teaching tactics that would allow pupils to grasp the information easily. Apart from that, the teacher's involvement is critical in ensuring a successful learning process. When the initial duty of a teacher is to educate, teach, aim, coach, assess, and evaluate young students of education at education formals and explain on topic, the teacher is considered as a professional educator.

A professional teacher, on the other hand, will develop good students and a competitive future in the globalization period. Teacher educators must also have effective teaching techniques so that the teaching process will be easier to offer and students will comprehend learning more easily, in order to reach the goal of teaching and learning. In fact, there are numerous options for strategies that a teacher can use

while teaching, not only in the classroom, but also outside the classroom, that make learning more interesting for students, so teachers must be active and creative in selecting teaching strategies that are better and more efficient for students so that the teacher can maintain a good and active control over the classroom.

A strategy is defined as a set of procedures for learning, thinking, teaching, and other activities. This is a strategy for achieving a specific goal. Every person has their own strategy for achieving their objectives. An approach stated by one teacher may differ from that of another. It is dependent on their pupils' requirements or the learning objectives they wish to achieve. As it is well known, determining which teaching technique to use in the classroom necessitates careful planning and design.

In order to create an environment where the interactions between students may happen, there are so many strategies can be applied. The specific activities manifested in the classroom that were consistent with a strategy and therefore were in harmony with approach as well. Consequently, teacher's strategies in teaching speaking to the students are really important.

Teaching strategy is a fundamental aspect of teaching for teachers. Furthermore, this institution encourages pupils to use bilingual skills in their daily lives. As a result, the research on teaching strategy can serve as a guide for schools looking to build and improve their qualities. It is well known that in order for students to understand, a teacher must have a teaching method.

Methods, or the process of teaching something, are born from an approach, and they involve classroom activities or procedures to assist learners learn. Following the approach, the strategy becomes a component of the approach. There are a variety of learning tactics and supporting references used by teachers in the classroom, including:

The first strategy is **Learning Strategy** that stresses a teacher's or educators verbal delivery of knowledge to trainees in order for them to grasp the subject matter to the best of their ability.

The second technique is **Problem-based learning strategy**, which involves teachers digging up the maximum capacity of students and the potential of students in completing the discharge of obligations / issues in the learning process. Learning objectives can be met if educational activities are centered on real, relevant, and contextual tasks or issues. Learning begins with problems, and these challenges will decide the path of group learning. Contextual Learning Strategies is the other strategy. Contextual Learning Strategies is a learning method that emphasizes the process of student involvement in order for them to be able to locate the material being studied and relate it to real-life circumstances, allowing them to use it in their lives.

Cooperative learning strategies is the third option. Cooperative learning Strategies are a set of learning activities that students in small groups with varying skills use to achieve pre-determined learning objectives.

Teachers need some theory strategies for teaching, especially when it came to teaching speaking, such as expository learning strategies, quantum learning strategies, cooperative learning strategies, and inquiry learning strategies, problem-based learning strategy, contextual learning strategies, and active learning strategies. Some tactics can be utilized to assist the teacher in teaching learning listening so that the teaching learning process is good and interesting. As a result, the technique is critical for teachers to correctly educate and present teaching materials, as well as to create a classroom atmosphere that is more entertaining and fascinating, resulting in the attainment of learning goals, particularly speaking comprehension.

Involving learners intentionally in their own learning process as they attempt to enhance their spoken English is one of the key focuses of improving spoken English. The goal of teaching speaking is to help pupils achieve four goals:

- a. To boost self-assurance when speaking and listening in English.
- b. To increase comprehensibility when speaking and listening to English.
- c. To increase English speaking fluency.

d. To increase the correctness with which one speaks English. Following the experts' explanations, the researcher concluded that teaching speaking is the activity of assisting students' learning processes through diverse tactics in order to achieve successful learning. When teaching speaking, it's crucial to understand the characteristics of spoken language that can influence certain aspects of speaking. Speaking ability is the ability to talk and interact with the interlocutor fluently and comprehensibly. Speaking activities in the classroom may be used to practice communicative competence. There are listed following characteristics of an effective speaking activity:

a. Students chat a lot. Learner discussion takes up as much time as feasible during the time given for the activity. This may seem self-evident, yet instructor chat or pauses typically consume the majority of time.

b. There is an even distribution of participation. A minority of talkative people does not dominate classroom discussion: everyone gets an opportunity to speak, and contributions are reasonably evenly divided.

b. There is a lot of motivation. Learners are motivated to talk for a variety of reasons: they are engaged in the issue and have something fresh to say about it, or they want to help achieve a task goal.

d. The level of language is acceptable. Learners express themselves in utterances that are relevant, easily understandable to one another, and have a high level of grammatical precision. When discussing techniques in English language education, it is impossible to differentiate strategy from approach at first.

The purpose of the interactional function is to form and sustain social relationships. In the meanwhile, transactional functions focused on information sharing. In this situation, speaking tries to transfer information from one person to another, which may involve two or more persons who utilize language for interaction and transactional purposes. People need to communicate in a variety of scenarios in their daily lives, including talking to someone face to face, conversing over the

phone, answering inquiries, asking for directions, shopping, meetings, and chatting with friends, to mention a few. People spend a lot of time communicating with other people, and each of these circumstances necessitates a distinct register depending on the formality of the situation. The objective of speaking, according to the experts, is to acquire excellent speaking skills that can be understood by classmates, instructors, staff, and others for academic and social purposes such as dialogues, classroom debates, and oral presentations.

Speaking ability is the language competence that is seen as the proof and the hallmark of language instruction and learning, as stated above. When speaking ability is discussed, the question that arises is to what extent learners can be deemed to have speaking ability. Speaking effectively depends very lot on the speakers' capacity to interact with an interlocutor. Communicative competence is judged according to the degree of fluency with the spoken language, but it also includes comprehension of that language in real-life situations.

References

1. Farrel, Thomas S.C. 2006. Succeeding with English Language Learners. Thousand Oaks: Corwin Press,
2. Harmer, J. 2012. The Practice of English language Teaching. Cambridge: Pearson Longman Press
Horwitz, Eliane K. 2001. Becoming A Language Teacher (A practical Guide to SecondLanguage Learning and Teaching. Boston: Pearson Education Inc
3. Hughes, Rebecca. 2002. Teaching and Researching Speaking. Harlow: Pearson Education
4. Orlich, D.C. et al., 2010. Teaching strategies a guide to effective instruction. Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company.
5. Richard, J. C., et al. 2012. Longman Dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics. Cambridge University